

QUERCETAGETIN FROM THE FLOWERS OF *TAGETES ERECTA*.

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Quercetagetin has been isolated from French marigold (Ganda) of Indian variety.

Quercetagetin (I), the yellow pigment of the flowers of *Tagetes patula* (the African marigold), was isolated by Latour and de la Source (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1877, ii, 28, 337; Perkin and Everest "The Natural Organic Colouring Matters", p. 230), according to whom it also occurs in other varieties of the plant whose names, however, are not mentioned in the paper. Perkin (*Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 19, 75) obtained the colouring matter in the pure state and showed that quercetagetin was 3:5:6:7:3':4'- (or 3:5:7:8:3':4'').

hexahydroxyflavone, the correctness of the first suggestion (and the identity of gossypetin with the second) being more recently demonstrated by synthesis (Baker, Nodzu and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 74).

The flowers of *Tagetes erecta* (the French marigold; *Hindi*, Ganda), a plant commonly cultivated in gardens throughout India, have now been examined and both the yellow and orange flowers shown to contain the same pigment as *Tagetes patula*. The substance is readily obtainable by the extraction method described by Perkin (*loc. cit.*), but a preliminary treatment with chloroform gave a better yield of more easily crystallisable material. The juice of the flowers of *Tagetes erecta* is reputed to have pharmacological properties as a purifier of the blood and as a remedy in piles (Nadkarni, "Indian Materia Medica", p. 834).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Immediately after collection the petals (1800 g.) of the orange flowers were carefully removed, dried in the air and extracted with chloroform in a Soxhlet for an hour. The colouring matter was then extracted with alcohol, the extraction being continued until the extract was colourless. The alcoholic solution was then reduced in bulk to 200 c.c. under diminished pressure and filtered hot to remove the dark brown resinous matter which had separated. After cooling the clear filtrate was mixed with ether and water, the ether layer separated and the ether removed. The bright yellow residue (13 g.) was acetylated by means of acetic anhydride and pyridine.

The product isolated on admixture with water was dark brown in colour, but when left in contact with glacial acetic acid overnight, the substance was obtained as a colourless, crystalline powder. Crystallisation from alcohol-acetic acid, followed by recrystallisation from methanol, gave colourless silky needles (7.5 g.), m.p. 210° . (Found : C, 56.7; H, 3.9. Calc. for $C_{27}H_{22}O_{14}$: C, 56.8; H, 3.9 per cent). Hydrolysis of the acetate (7 g.) was effected by dissolution in boiling glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.) and gradual addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.). Boiling water (100 c.c.) was then added and, on cooling, quercetagenin separated in long, silky, pale brownish yellow needles (3.5 g.). m. p. 317° (decomp.). The substance crystallises from alcohol with two molecules of water [Found by heating at 160° for 3 hours : H_2O , 9.9. $C_{15}H_{10}O_8$, $2H_2O$ requires H_2O , 10.1 per cent. Found (in the dried material) : C, 56.5; H, 3.4. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{10}O_8$: C, 56.5; H, 3.2 per cent]. The pure substance is readily soluble in boiling alcohol and sparingly soluble in boiling water in which the impure pigment is fairly soluble. The alcoholic solution of the flavone exhibits an olive green colouration with ferric chloride; with lead acetate an orange-red precipitate is formed, which gradually turns yellow and finally green. The brownish yellow solution in concentrated sulphuric acid develops a bluish green fluorescence on standing.

Quercetagenin Hexamethylether.—To a mixture of the hexacetate (6.5 g.) and acetone (50 c.c.) in a three-necked flask equipped with a mercury-seal stirrer, an inlet and outlet for hydrogen and two dropping funnels, dimethyl sulphate (37.5 g.) and 50% aqueous caustic soda (15.4 g.) were added simultaneously drop by drop, the reaction mixture being tested for alkalinity from time to time. During the addition of the first 100 c.c. the mixture was yellow in colour and a dark green oil separated at the bottom. Further addition of methyl sulphate and alkali initiated a vigorous reaction, which rapidly became violent and was controlled by cooling in running water. After the complete addition of the reagents (3 hours), the whole reaction mixture became clear, pale orange; the stirring was continued for 30 minutes and on pouring into water (1 litre) the bright yellow product was collected and twice crystallised from acetone in long, pale yellow needles, m. p. 142° , yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 62.3; H, 5.3. Calc. for $C_{27}H_{22}O_8$: C, 62.7; H, 5.5 per cent). When the molten substance solidified and the m.p. was again observed it was found to be 155° (*cf.* Perkin *loc. cit.*; Baker, Nodzu and Robinson, *loc. cit.*).

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